

**ISSUES TO BE ADDRESSED WHEN INTERROGATING
WITNESSES (HOMICIDE)**

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Abstract

In this article, the criminalistic aspects of questioning witnesses and witnesses are analyzed using the example of the crime of murder. In addition, the aspects of witness responsibility and the main aspects resolved by the investigator during the interrogation are considered.

Keywords: witness, murder, interrogation, investigative action, external signs.

The Criminal Procedure Code includes “witness” among other persons participating in criminal proceedings, and any person who may be aware of any circumstance to be clarified in a criminal case may be summoned to testify as a

witness.

Along with persons participating in criminal proceedings, a witness also has their rights and obligations, in particular, the right to use the legal assistance of a lawyer, the services of an interpreter, to familiarize themselves with interrogation protocols, and to file a complaint.

The witness also has the right not to testify against himself. However, sometimes the perpetrator may be involved in the case as a witness, and if he does not testify against himself and adds false information to his testimony, he may be prosecuted for giving false testimony. We do not consider this aspect justified.

In addition, the witness has obligations to appear at the summons of the investigator, inquiry officer, prosecutor, and court;

to truthfully report on everything known to him in the case;

answer the questions posed;

not to disclose the circumstances known to him in the case without the permission of the interrogator;

observe order during the investigation of the case and the court session.

Moreover, if a witness refuses to testify or gives false testimony, they may be held liable *under Articles 238 and 240 of the Criminal Code*.

Issues to be resolved during witness questioning (for murder): Depending on the type of crime, the investigator develops typical investigative situations and investigative hypotheses. Decides the sequence of investigative actions to be carried out, what aspects to focus on, and who to involve in the investigative process.

Similarly, when a murder is committed, interrogation is carried out along with several investigative actions. The procedure and methods of interrogation depend on

who is being interrogated. For interrogation, in general, in all crimes, persons are involved in the status of witnesses, victims, accused, and suspects.

In the course of our analysis, we will talk about the issues resolved during the interrogation of witnesses in the crime of murder.

First of all, it is necessary to try to clarify from witnesses the circumstances under which the murder was committed. That is, first, general information, all events witnessed by witnesses should be clarified, and information about the time, circumstances of the crime, and characteristics of the persons should be requested.

Secondly, it is necessary to clarify the direction of movement of the murderer after committing the crime and information about the transport used by him. Because catching this killer faster serves to prevent his escape or concealment. For example, a witness may have memorized his car number.

Thirdly, what objects the murderer took with him from the scene. For example, the instrument of the crime can be an object belonging to the victim, money, or valuables. Through this, it is possible to qualify the crime or determine the cause of the crime.

Fourthly, it is necessary to determine the degree of acquaintance of the murderer with the interrogated person.

For example, a witness may know that the victim and the murderer were previously acquainted, or may have seen them together before. The witness may know the identity of the murderer, but they may not recognize him.

Therefore, the next aspect that needs to be clarified is the external characteristics of the killer. By depicting the killer's external features, his portrait can be drawn, and through this, the killer's identity can be identified.

Fifthly, what was the witness engaged in during the murder. That is, one can know how accurately he was aware of the events, whether he had the opportunity to do so or not. Sometimes individuals may give false or unsubstantiated testimony, or they may have committed the murder themselves. No one is considered a criminal until proven guilty and a guilty verdict is issued by the court. All investigative actions serve to quickly clarify the investigative versions and solve the crime.

Sixthly, to determine whether the murderer left any objects or items at the crime scene. In some cases, witnesses may seize items from the scene, or the perpetrator may leave an item at the scene and take it back.

The abandoned items can serve to establish the identity of the criminal, his direction.

For example, a murderer's purchase receipt can also be used to identify the murderer through the cameras of the location where he made the purchase.

Seventhly, to find out who else witnessed the incident. If there are many witnesses, each of them must be interrogated separately and verified that they did not give testimony contradicting each other's statements, and that the events and persons they described are identical.

Thus, we have briefly analyzed the issues that should be considered when questioning witnesses in a murder case. We can add many more aspects to the above general issues. This varies depending on the incident and witness testimonies.

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